

Improving Estimates of Lunar Surface Temperature and Derived Emissivity Spectrums from Remote Infrared Instrumentation: Laboratory Validation of LTM's Brightness Temperature Estimation.

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Introduction: Since July 2009, estimations of lunar surface temperatures have been measured from the Diviner Lunar Radiometer Experiment (Diviner), a multi-spectral instrument observing mid- and far-infrared on NASA's Lunar Reconnaissance Orbiter (LRO) [1]. The Lunar Thermal Mapper (LTM) on Lunar Trailblazer (a small-sat SIMPLEX mission launched February 26, 2025) was designed and built by the University of Oxford's Space Instrumentation Group within the Physics Department, to improve upon current infrared instrumentation (e.g., Diviner) and surface temperature estimations [2, 3]. Accurately defining surface temperatures of airless bodies is critical for interpreting infrared spectral features, such as the Christiansen Feature, and correctly understanding the thermal-physical environment [5, 8].

In preparation for the Trailblazer mission, our team tested and validated LTM's methods for brightness temperature (BT) estimation, including a comparison to Diviner's method for BT retrieval. In this work, we aim to: 1) investigate methods for defining a maximum BT that yields the most representative surface temperature estimate and (2) subsequently identify how BT estimates affect emissivity spectra analysis. Despite the current challenges facing Trailblazer, refining methods for BT retrieval remains relevant to the planetary surfaces community as numerous future missions will depend on infrared instrumentation for remote or in-situ analysis (e.g., LEAP, Europa Clipper).

Instrumentation and Temperature Retrieval:

Diviner is a nine-channel radiometer with wavelengths from 0.3 to 400 μm (Table 1) [1]. Channels 3 (7.55 - 8.05 μm), 4 (8.10 - 8.40 μm), and 5 (8.38-8.60 μm) are three narrow passbands used to identify the Christiansen Feature (CF), an emissivity maximum that is diagnostic of bulk silicate mineralogy [1,4]. Diviner estimates BT by fitting a parabola to its three compositional channels and identifying the peak of the parabolic fit as the maximum BT. Emissivity is calculated as the ratio of the observed radiance to that of a blackbody at the BT maximum. The wavelength at the peak of a parabolic fit to the emissivity spectrum defines the CF.

LTM is a fifteen-channel multispectral infrared imager with wavelengths from 6 to 100 μm [2, 3]. Eleven narrow band channels (6.25 - 10 μm) on LTM were selected to advance the breadth of Thermal Infrared (TIR) spectral feature

characterization, capturing the CF, Reststrahlen bands, and transparency features (Table 1) [2,3]. This study validates the temperature estimation methods in LTM's Narrowband (compositional) spectral region.

Table 1: LTM and Diviner observational parameters.

Parameters	LTM	Diviner
Resolution	40-70m/pixel	~200m/pixel
Broadband (Thermal)	110 - 400 K ($\pm < 2$ K) (6- 100 μm)	30 - 400 K (0.6 - 400 μm)
Narrowband (Compositional)	11 Channels (7-10 μm)	3 Channels (7.5 - 8.6 μm)

Methodology: Laboratory Analysis: Four volcanic samples, Twin Sisters-1 and Twin Sisters-2 (dunite), BIR-1 (Icelandic basalt), and RGM-1 (rhyolite), were measured under ambient conditions (1000 bar, N₂ atmosphere, sample heated to 350 K) using the Planetary Analogue Surface Chamber for Asteroids and Lunar Environments (PASCALE), and a Bruker Vertex 70V vacuum Fourier transform Infrared (FTIR) spectrometer [4]. PASCALE is a vacuum chamber capable of simulating near-surface environments of airless bodies, such as the moon (at $< 10^{-4}$ mbar). In isolation, the FTIR spectrometer measures sample reflectance; paired with PASCALE, the spectrometer captures sample emission, providing a more accurate representation of infrared signals detected by orbiting instruments. Spectra were recorded over ~ the 6000 to 50 cm^{-1} range at 4 cm^{-1} resolution. Further details of QA/QC protocols and procedures are described in [6,7,8].

Brightness Temperature (BT) and Emissivity Estimations: The radiance of each sample was convolved with the LTM filter response to test the BT estimation methods on 'LTM resolution' data. Seven methods were used to determine the maximum BT (derived via the Planck function) from the LTM-resolution data of each sample (Table 2). Emissivity was then calculated as the ratio of the observed LTM-resolution radiance to that of a blackbody at the maximum BT for the seven methods across all samples. By benchmarking each method against the known laboratory sample temperature (350 K) and emissivity data, we were able to validate LTM's BT estimation methods. A targeted comparison was then conducted to evaluate discrepancies between temperature estimation methods, including those based on the Diviner approach.

Table 2: Descriptions of Brightness Temperature (BT) estimation methods.

BT Method	Description
Diviner	A parabolic fit is applied to Diviner's 3 narrowband channels (which overlap with LTM) with the maximum BT taken as the peak of the fitted parabola.
Quadratic	A parabolic fit is applied to five points around the maximum of LTM's 11 narrowband channels with the maximum BT taken as the peak of the fitted parabola.
3rd degree Polynomial	A cubic polynomial fit is applied to five points around the maximum of LTM's 11 narrowband channels with the maximum BT taken as the peak of the fitted cubic.
Spline	A cubic spline interpolation is applied to all of LTM's 11 narrowband channels with the maximum BT taken as the peak of the fitted spline.
Narrowband Average	The maximum BT is taken as the average temperature of LTM's 11 narrowband channels.
Narrowband Max	The maximum BT is taken as the highest temperature among LTM's 11 narrowband channels.

Results and Discussion: The 3rd-degree polynomial, spline, quadratic, and narrowband maximum BT estimation methods best reflect the laboratory spectra. Temperature variances (standard error, SE) for each composition did not differ drastically between methods (Table 3). Since the spline fit does not offer significant improvement over the 3rd-degree polynomial fit, the quadratic fit, or the narrowband maximum, these simpler methods are favoured for LTM temperature estimation (max SE: 3.42%). With fewer narrowband channels, Diviner underestimates surface temperatures up to 19 K (max SE: 5.55%) for TS-2 (dunite) (Table 3). Further testing across a broader range of compositions is necessary to evaluate whether Diviner's BT estimates shift the CF wavenumber and spectral shape compared to the other BT estimation methods.

Table 3: BT methods with temperature estimates and associated standard error (SE) with composition.

BT Method	TS-1		TS-2		RGM-1		BIR-1	
	T(K)	SE (%)	T(K)	SE (%)	T(K)	SE (%)	T(K)	SE (%)
Diviner	348	0.51	331	5.55	343	2.14	337	3.72
Quadratic	344	1.5	338	3.32	343	2.14	338	3.42
3rd deg. Polynomial	344	1.6	339	3.18	343	2.14	338	3.42
Spline	344	1.65	339	3.27	343	2.15	338	3.44
Narrowband Average	343	2.14	336	3.92	342	2.41	337	3.65
Narrowband Max	344	1.61	339	3.16	343	2.14	338	3.42

Fig 2: Seven temperature estimation methods are fitted to laboratory emissivity spectra of four lunar analogues (dunite, basalt, and rhyolite).

Conclusions: Preliminary investigations comparing Diviner and LTM temperature estimation methods demonstrate that the 3rd-degree polynomial, quadratic, or narrowband maximum (max SE: 3.42%) methods provide the most accurate fits to laboratory spectra. Diviner temperature estimations underestimate surface temperatures by a maximum of 19K; however, the spectral shape and the wavelength range for laboratory spectra are maintained. Expanding the spectral library may illuminate whether CF shifts in wavenumber occur across compositions when using the Diviner method.

References: [1] Paige D.A. (2010) et al. Space Science Review, doi:10.1007/s11214-009-9529-2 [2] Ehlmann B.L. et al. (2022) IEEE Aerospace Conference, 1-14, doi:10.1109/AERO53065.2022.9843663 [3] Bowles N.E. et al. (2025) LPSC, 56, 2382. [4] Husic A. et al. (2022) LPSC, 53, #2056. [5] Greenhagen B.T. et al. (2010) Science, 329, 1507-1509 doi:10.1126/science.1192196. [6] Donaldson Hannah K.L. et al. (2012) JGR, 117, doi:10.1029/2011JE003862. [7] Donaldson Hannah K.L. et al. (2017) Icarus, 283, 326-342. [8] Donaldson Hannah K.L. et al. (2021) JGR Plan-ets, 126, e2020JE006624.